

STUDY OF SOIL MOISTURE STATUS AND RELATIVE LEAF WATER CONTENT (RLWC) OF MAIZE AS INFLUENCED BY APPLICATION OF HYDROGEL AND MULCHING IN SANDY SOIL

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Abstract

An experiment was conducted to study the soil moisture status and Relative Leaf Water Content (RLWC) of maize as influenced by application of hydrogel and mulching in sandy soil. Randomised block design with two factors (hydrogel and mulching) with three levels each and one additional control was used to laid out the research work. Different levels of hydrogel and types of mulches, their interactions and a control were analysed statistically. With regards to moisture content of soil, application of rice straw mulch @ 5 t ha⁻¹ recorded maximum moisture content (15 and 30 cm depth) at all the stages of crop growth. Hydrogel applied @ 3.75 kg ha⁻¹ recorded maximum moisture content at 15 and 30 cm depth at all the stages of the crop growth except at harvest stage where hydrogel effect was non-significant and was on par with hydrogel @ 2.5 kg ha⁻¹ at 60 DAS (15 cm depth). In general, among the interactions, high soil moisture content at 15 and 30 cm depth was found with hydrogel @ 3.75 kg ha⁻¹ and rice straw mulch @ 5 t ha⁻¹ at all the stages under observation. RLWC recorded maximum in treatments in which hydrogel applied @ 1.25 kg ha⁻¹ at 30 DAS and hydrogel @ 2.5 kg ha⁻¹ at 60 and 90 DAS. In case of types of mulch, rice straw mulch @ 5 t ha⁻¹ at 30 and 60 DAS and coirpith compost mulch @ 2.5 t ha⁻¹ at 90 DAS recorded maximum RLWC. Control recorded lower soil moisture content and RLWC than the remaining treatments.

Key words – Hydrogel, mulch, soil moisture, RLWC.

Introduction

The issue of water management has assumed paramount importance and occupy the centre stage of politico-economic debates in world. The sharp fall in groundwater levels due to excessive removal for agricultural and other uses coupled with the high cost of fuel and electrical energy used in drawing groundwater and poor water use efficiency (WUE) due to wasteful practices are affecting the economics of water use in all spheres of human activity. The situation is forcing the researchers to search for viable technological options to meet future water needs. Poor use efficiency of water is the major bottleneck in attaining sustainable agricultural development, food safety and security in future. These goals can be achieved only with the rational and scientific management of production inputs. Many agronomical practices were developed and suggested to increase WUE in crops. However, a complete strategy to develop combined solutions for several difficulties has been indefinable. The practices like limited irrigation scheduling, application of mulches and hydrophilic polymer (hydrogel) has increased the duration of moisture availability with an increase in the amount of available moisture in the soil.

Maize (*Zea mays* L.) is widely grown crop throughout the world after rice and wheat. The crop which is most sensitive to low and high moisture stress. So, proper irrigation management enhanced the maize yield significantly.

Hydrogel application preserved the water and increased the capability of soil to store moisture, ensured its availability, increased RLWC and finally increased the plant growth under moisture stress condition (Kramer, 1988). Generally sandy soils are having less water holding capability. Application of hydrogel at 0.4 % increases the water holding capacity, maintains proper infiltration of water and reduces the deep percolation losses (Al-Darby, 1996).

Sandy soils were amended with hydrogel @ 0, 0.5, 1.0 and 2.0 % (w/w) and water retaining curve of sandy soil was found by using Richard's pressure plate apparatus. Hydrogel changed the soil water holding properties. Soil moisture at FC showed 400 % increase in the water holding capacity when amended with hydrogel than control and at PWP also showed similar results. There was an increase in the stored moisture content and saturated moisture content in available moisture tension range (0-15 bars) and available moisture in the soil enhanced 2.3 times than the control (Koupai *et al.*, 2008).

Shading is very effective at initial-stages of drying a wet top soil (Adams *et al.*, 1976). Mulching decreases evaporation of soil moisture mainly through covering top soil from sun (Li *et al.*, 2008). Finally, significant increase in soil-moisture storage under mulching because of reduction in soil evaporation (Singh *et al.*, 2015).

Materials and Methods

A research programme was conducted at CoA, Padannakkad, KAU, Thrissur, Kerala during *rabi*, 2017. Experiment was laid out in randomised block design with two factors (hydrogel and mulching) and an extra treatment (control). Both factors having three levels each. Three levels of hydrogel H₁ – 1.25 kg ha⁻¹, H₂ – 2.5 kg ha⁻¹ and H₃ – 3.75 kg ha⁻¹ and three types of mulch M₁ – rice straw mulch, M₂ – rice husk mulch, M₃ – Coirpith compost mulch were used in the experiment. Straw mulch and rice husk mulch were applied @ 5 t ha⁻¹ and coirpith compost mulch was applied @ 2.5 t ha⁻¹. The treatment combinations were T₁ - 1.25 kg ha⁻¹ hydrogel + rice straw mulch, T₂ - 1.25 kg ha⁻¹ hydrogel + rice husk mulch, T₃ - 1.25 kg ha⁻¹ hydrogel + Coirpith compost mulch, T₄ - 2.5 kg ha⁻¹ hydrogel + rice straw mulch, T₅ - 2.5 kg ha⁻¹ hydrogel + rice husk mulch, T₆ - 2.5 kg ha⁻¹ hydrogel + coirpith compost mulch, T₇ - 3.75 kg ha⁻¹ hydrogel + rice straw mulch, T₈ - 3.75 kg ha⁻¹ hydrogel + rice husk mulch, T₉ - 3.75 kg ha⁻¹ hydrogel + coirpith compost mulch, T₁₀ - control (without hydrogel and mulch). Soil moisture content at 15 cm and 30 cm was estimated before irrigation at 30, 60, 90 and harvest stage by using the gravimetric method of soil moisture estimation given by Reynolds (1970). The observation on RLWC found by using the method proposed by Weatherley (1950) which was later modified by Slatyer and Barrs (1965) was used to estimate RLWC at 30, 60 and 90 DAS and it was expressed in %. The formula for estimating RLWC is

$$RLWC = \frac{\text{Fresh weight} - \text{Dry weight}}{\text{Turgid weight} - \text{Dry weight}} \times 100$$
Results and Discussion**Soil moisture**

At 30 and 90 DAS and at harvest stage the maximum soil moisture content at 15 cm depth was noticed with rice straw mulch @ 5 t ha⁻¹ (4.14 %, 4.19 % and 2.24 % respectively) which was significantly superior to other types of mulch and at harvest stage it was on par with the rice husk mulch @ 5 t ha⁻¹ (Table 1). At all stages (30, 60, 90 DAS and harvest stage) the maximum soil moisture content at 30 cm depth was recorded by rice straw mulch @ 5 t ha⁻¹ (4.35 %, 3.58 %, 4.35 % and 3.37 % respectively) which was significantly superior to other types of mulch except at 60 DAS. At 60 DAS it was on par with coirpith compost mulch. This might be due to better soil surface coverage offered by straw mulch than the other mulches resulted in reduced evaporation from the soil. The insignificant effect of different types of mulch on soil moisture at 15 cm depth at 60 DAS may be attributed to the shading effect of plant canopy on the soil surface.

In case of levels of hydrogels, maximum soil moisture content (15 cm depth) was observed at 30, 60 and 90 DAS, when hydrogel was applied @ 3.75 kg ha⁻¹ (4.01 %, 3.45 % and 4.20 % respectively) and

was significantly superior to other two levels of hydrogel. Maximum soil moisture content (30 cm depth) at 30, 60, 90 DAS and harvest stage was observed in hydrogel level @ 3.75 kg ha⁻¹ (4.14 %, 3.53 %, 4.55 % and 3.42 % respectively) and was on par with hydrogel level @ 2.5 kg ha⁻¹ at 60 DAS.

In general, among the interactions the high soil moisture content at 15 and 30 cm depth was found with hydrogel @ 3.75 kg ha⁻¹ and rice straw mulch @ 5 t ha⁻¹ at all the stages under observation (Fig. 1 and 2). High moisture content in hydrogel applied treatment @ 3.75 kg ha⁻¹ was due to storing of moisture by the hydrogel and slow release to the soil in accordance with decrease in the soil moisture content.

The increase in soil moisture content over control was worked out at harvest stage. The results indicated that there was pronounced increase in soil moisture at 30 cm depth due to application of hydrogel, mulch and their combinations. Application of hydrogel @ 3.75 kg ha⁻¹ recorded an increase of 84.86 % and rice straw mulch recorded 82.16% over absolute control. A cumulative increase of 126.49 % was observed when hydrogel @ 3.75 kg ha⁻¹ was combined with rice straw mulch @ 5 t ha⁻¹ which was followed by H₂M₁ (92.43%) and H₃M₃ (80.00 %).

Comparison of soil moisture content of control with other treatment revealed that soil moisture at 15 cm depth in control was significantly lower than other treatments at 30, 60, 90 DAS and at harvest stage. Increased soil moisture content due to straw mulching was also observed by Shen *et al.* (2012) and Zhao *et al.* (2014) and increased soil moisture content by hydrogel application was reported by Koupai *et al.* (2008) and Nazarli *et al.* (2010) in sandy soil.

Table 1. Effect of hydrogel and mulching on soil moisture content at 15 cm and 30 cm depth

Treatment of hydrogel	Soil moisture at 15 cm depth (%)				Soil moisture at 30 cm depth (%)				% increase over control at harvest
	30 DAS	60 DAS	90 DAS	At harvest	30 DAS	60 DAS	90 DAS	At harvest	
H ₁	3.32	2.42	3.32	1.94	3.57	2.86	3.46	2.40	29.73
H ₂	3.75	3.18	3.90	2.07	3.92	3.50	4.11	2.98	61.08
H ₃	4.01	3.45	4.20	2.04	4.14	3.53	4.55	3.42	84.86
SEm (±)	0.090	0.225	0.061	0.156	0.061	0.198	0.076	0.103	
CD (0.05)	0.190	0.472	0.127	NS	0.128	0.415	0.159	0.217	
Types of mulch									
M ₁	4.14	3.21	4.19	2.24	4.35	3.58	4.35	3.37	82.16
M ₂	3.36	2.88	3.59	2.01	3.57	2.92	3.80	2.53	36.76
M ₃	3.57	2.96	3.64	1.80	3.71	3.39	3.97	2.90	56.76
SEm (±)	0.090	0.225	0.061	0.156	0.061	0.198	0.076	0.103	
CD (0.05)	0.190	NS	0.127	0.328	0.128	0.415	0.159	0.217	
Interactions									
H ₁ M ₁	3.35	2.81	3.54	2.05	3.77	3.43	3.56	2.37	28.11
H ₁ M ₂	3.29	2.23	3.14	1.84	3.38	2.46	3.31	2.29	23.78
H ₁ M ₃	3.31	2.23	3.28	1.93	3.55	2.68	3.52	2.53	36.76
H ₂ M ₁	4.30	3.09	4.10	2.71	4.40	2.77	4.42	3.56	92.43
H ₂ M ₂	3.34	2.69	3.76	1.95	3.65	3.68	3.91	2.56	38.38
H ₂ M ₃	3.60	3.75	3.83	1.55	3.71	4.06	3.99	2.83	52.97
H ₃ M ₁	4.78	3.73	4.60	1.97	4.88	4.53	5.07	4.19	126.49
H ₃ M ₂	3.44	3.71	3.86	2.24	3.68	2.62	4.18	2.75	48.65
H ₃ M ₃	3.81	2.90	3.80	1.91	3.87	3.43	4.39	3.33	80.00
SEm (±)	0.156	0.389	0.105	0.271	0.106	0.342	0.076	0.179	
CD (0.05)	0.329	0.817	0.221	0.569	0.222	0.719	0.159	0.376	
Control vs other treatments									
Control	1.74	1.95	2.96	1.33	2.11	3.25	2.92	1.85	
SEm (±)	0.117	0.290	0.078	0.202	0.079	0.255	0.098	0.133	
CD (0.05)	0.245	0.609	0.164	0.424	0.165	NS	0.206	0.280	

Note: H₁ - hydrogel @ 1.25 kg ha⁻¹, H₂ - hydrogel @ 2.5 kg ha⁻¹, H₃ - hydrogel @ 3.75 kg ha⁻¹, M₁ - rice straw mulch @ 5 t ha⁻¹, M₂ - rice husk mulch @ 5 t ha⁻¹, M₃ - coirpith compost mulch @ 2.5 t ha⁻¹.

Table 2. Effect of hydrogel and mulching on RLWC (%)

Treatment	RLWC (%)
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Relative Leaf Water Content (RLWC)

At 30 DAS maximum RLWC was observed where hydrogel was applied @ 1.25 kg ha⁻¹ (89.75 %) which was on par with hydrogel level @ 3.75 kg ha⁻¹ (Table 2). At 60 and 90 DAS maximum RLWC was observed where hydrogel was applied @ 2.5 kg ha⁻¹ (90.81 % and 88.97 % respectively) which was on par with hydrogel level @ 3.75 kg ha⁻¹ at 60 DAS and was significantly superior to other levels of hydrogel at 90 DAS. At 30 and 60 DAS the maximum RLWC was noticed with rice straw mulch @ 5 t ha⁻¹ (90.82 % and 91.45 % respectively) which was significantly superior to other types of mulch. At 90 DAS the maximum RLWC was noticed in coirpith mulch @ 2.5 t ha⁻¹ (88.04 %) which was significantly superior to other types of mulch. In general, among the interactions of levels of hydrogel and types of mulch maximum RLWC was recorded with the treatments with different levels of hydrogel and rice straw mulch @ 5 t ha⁻¹ at 30 and 60 DAS. When compared with RLWC of control with other treatments, at all stages (30, 60 and 90 DAS) RLWC showed significant difference between control and other treatments. Control recorded a lower RLWC than the other treatments. Decreased moisture content of plant resulted in decreased cell volume due to lower turgor pressure and consequent increase in solute concentration in cells. Application of hydrogel and rice straw mulch increased the turgor pressure inside the cells by maintaining adequate amount of moisture as per plant need and reduced the evaporation losses by covering the soil surface.

Levels of hydrogel	30 DAS	60 DAS	90 DAS
H ₁	89.75	89.12	84.70
H ₂	88.47	90.81	88.97
H ₃	89.32	90.40	85.85
SEm (±)	0.357	0.376	0.745
CD (0.05)	0.750	0.790	1.566
Types of mulch			
M ₁	90.82	91.45	86.44
M ₂	87.07	88.91	85.04
M ₃	89.66	89.96	88.04
SEm (±)	0.357	0.376	0.745
CD (0.05)	0.750	0.790	1.566
Interactions			
H ₁ M ₁	92.55	90.23	86.16
H ₁ M ₂	86.14	86.42	81.12
H ₁ M ₃	90.57	90.71	86.80
H ₂ M ₁	89.30	91.44	86.55
H ₂ M ₂	86.29	91.26	91.70
H ₂ M ₃	89.82	89.74	88.65
H ₃ M ₁	90.60	92.68	86.59
H ₃ M ₂	88.77	89.07	82.30
H ₃ M ₃	88.60	89.44	88.66
SEm (±)	0.618	0.651	1.291
CD (0.05)	1.299	1.368	2.712
Control vs other treatments			
Control	86.04	85.80	78.79
SEm (±)	0.461	0.485	0.962
CD (0.05)	0.968	1.019	2.022

H₁ - hydrogel @ 1.25 kg ha⁻¹, H₂- hydrogel @ 2.5 kg ha⁻¹,
 H₃ - hydrogel @ 3.75 kg ha⁻¹, M₁ - rice straw mulch @ 5 t ha⁻¹,
 M₂ - rice husk mulch @ 5 t ha⁻¹, M₃ - coirpith compost mulch @ 2.5 t ha⁻¹.

Fig. 1. Effect of hydrogel and mulch on soil moisture content (%) at 15 cm depth

Fig. 2. Effect of hydrogel and mulch on soil moisture content (%) at 30 cm depth

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